

The Role of Hormones in the Regulation of Pregnancy and Fetal Development

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Abstract: Hormones play a central role in the regulation of pregnancy and fetal development, orchestrating processes from conception to birth. Key hormones, including human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), progesterone, estrogens, and placental hormones, ensure proper implantation, support the growth of the fetus, and prepare the maternal body for childbirth. This review summarizes the functions of these hormones, their interactions, and their influence on fetal organogenesis and maternal adaptations. Additionally, the article discusses hormonal imbalances that may lead to pregnancy complications and explores emerging therapeutic strategies.

Keywords: obesity, pregnancy, insulin resistance, gestational diabetes, ghrelin, leptin.

Introduction

Pregnancy is a complex physiological state requiring precise coordination between the maternal body and the developing fetus. Hormones serve as critical mediators, regulating implantation, placental function, fetal growth, and maternal adaptations. Understanding these hormonal mechanisms provides insights into normal and pathological pregnancies, aiding in the development of interventions for complications such as preeclampsia, preterm labor, and fetal growth restriction.

Obesity—one of the most socially significant chronic diseases that has reached epidemic proportions, with obesity in pregnant women attracting increasing attention. Despite constant improvements in the antenatal care and obstetrics system, the number of obese pregnant women is constantly increasing, which makes this issue especially important. The review covers the main mechanisms of obesity and hormonal disorders during pregnancy, risks and complications associated with obesity during pregnancy. Measures for preventing excess weight before and during pregnancy are outlined.

Obesity is one of the most socially significant chronic diseases, which has reached epidemic proportions (according to WHO). The constantly growing rate of obesity worldwide, as well as the increased morbidity and mortality associated with obesity, have made it one of the most pressing problems of modern health care, with obesity in pregnant women attracting increasing attention. Despite constant improvements in the antenatal care and obstetrics system, the number of obese pregnant women in economically developed countries reaches 15.5–26.9% and is constantly increasing, which is why the relevance of this problem is of particular importance [9].

Hormonal Regulation of Pregnancy

1. Human Chorionic Gonadotropin (hCG)

Secreted by the trophoblast shortly after implantation, hCG maintains corpus luteum function during early pregnancy, ensuring sustained progesterone production. hCG also promotes placental development and modulates maternal immune tolerance.

2. Progesterone

Produced initially by the corpus luteum and later by the placenta, progesterone maintains uterine quiescence by inhibiting myometrial contractions. It supports endometrial receptivity for implantation and contributes to immune modulation to prevent fetal rejection.

3. Estrogens

Estrogens (estradiol, estriol, and estrone) increase uterine blood flow and stimulate the growth of uterine and breast tissues. Estriol levels, produced predominantly by the placenta, serve as a marker of fetal well-being.

4. Placental Hormones

Human Placental Lactogen (hPL): Enhances maternal glucose metabolism and lipolysis to provide energy substrates for fetal growth. Placental Growth Hormone: Regulates maternal insulin-like growth factor (IGF) levels, supporting fetal growth and placental development.

During pregnancy, favorable conditions are created for the development of adipose tissue, the biological meaning of which is the metabolic protection of the unborn child.

From the first days of pregnancy, hormonal changes begin in the woman's body: increased synthesis of progesterone, human chorionic gonadotropin, prolactin and placental lactogen, stimulating the deposition of adipose tissue in the body. It is known that the distribution of adipose tissue is mainly determined by the hormones of the sex glands and the adrenal cortex, with the conversion of androgens into estrogens in adipocytes playing an important role. Adipose tissue, primarily visceral, has high hormonal-metabolic activity, contains a large number of adrenoreceptors, corticosteroid and androgen receptors, and is also capable of accumulating various steroids, such as testosterone, androstenedione, cortisol, due to their solubility in lipids. The main synthesis of sex hormones occurs in the ovaries, and adipocytes are the site of extragonadal synthesis of estrogens from androgens by aromatization and conversion of androstenedione and testosterone into estrone, and then it is converted into a more active estrogen - estradiol. In obesity, peripheral aromatization of androgens into estrogens increases, resulting in disruption of the metabolism of androgens and estrogens [2, 7]. Estrogen metabolism in obesity changes due to a decrease in the formation of inactive metabolites of estradiol, especially 2-hydroxyestrogens, and an increase in the amount of estrone sulfate, resulting in a change in the ratio of active and inactive estrogens in favor of active ones and the development of relative hyperestrogenemia, which can lead to the development of hyperplastic processes of the endometrium and ovarian dysfunction. The estrogen ratio during pregnancy is changed mainly due to the increase in the production of estriol, which has low activity but is secreted in very large quantities, due to which its effect during pregnancy is much stronger than that of other estrogens. The content of estradiol and estrone during pregnancy increases by a hundred times, and estriol by a thousand times [6]. A greater amount of estrogens after the 5th–7th week of pregnancy is formed in the syncytiotrophoblasts of the placenta due to their synthesis from dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate coming from the fetal blood. The main function of estrogens during pregnancy is to increase blood flow in the uterus due to the activation of prostaglandin synthesis. Androgen metabolism in obesity can change due to an increase in their free fractions (free testosterone) with the development of relative hyperandrogenism, which is associated with a low concentration of sex steroid-binding globulin. During pregnancy, both the production and inactivation of androgens increases due to an increase in the rate of their metabolic clearance, which leads to the maintenance of a normal ratio of circulating androgen levels, however, in 20–50% of obese pregnant women, a significant increase in androgen levels (testosterone, dehydroepiandrosterone, dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate) may be observed, and hyperandrogenism develops, which can lead to miscarriage [3].

One of the main mechanisms of the influence of sex hormones on adipose tissue is the direct stimulation by estrogens of the activity of lipoprotein lipase, an enzyme that regulates the accumulation of triglycerides in adipocytes and causes the deposition of adipose tissue mainly in the thighs and buttocks, where the activity of this enzyme is higher than in the adipose tissue of the abdominal region. As a result, lipids accumulate to ensure adequate energy reserves during pregnancy and lactation. Progesterone, the content of which increases during pregnancy, also participates in the regulation of adipose tissue deposition. It is known that progesterone competes with glucocorticoids for their receptors in adipocytes, thus preventing the lipolytic effect of glucocorticoids on adipose tissue. As a result of increased activity of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal system during pregnancy,

the production of tropic hormones (somatotropic, prolactin, adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH)) increases. Due to the increased formation of ACTH, the hormonal activity of the adrenal glands increases, the synthesis of glucocorticoids (cortisol) and mineralocorticoids (aldosterone) increases, which is an adaptation of the female body to the necessary activation of vital processes to meet the needs of the developing fetus.

Hormonal Influences on Fetal Development

1. Thyroid Hormones

Maternal thyroid hormones cross the placenta, playing a vital role in early brain and skeletal development. Fetal thyroid function becomes active in the second trimester, ensuring proper metabolic regulation

2. Glucocorticoids

Essential for fetal lung maturation, glucocorticoids prepare the lungs for air breathing by stimulating surfactant production. Dysregulation may contribute to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR).

3. Insulin-Like Growth Factors (IGFs)

IGFs mediate fetal growth, influenced by maternal and placental hormones. Abnormal IGF signaling is linked to growth abnormalities.

The ACTH level during pregnancy increases almost twofold, partly due to placental ACTH, which is not suppressed by glucocorticoids, but maintains a normal circadian rhythm. Due to increased ACTH production during pregnancy, the total amount of cortisol increases two to three times. Also, due to increased estrogen synthesis, the binding of cortisol to protein (corticosteroid-binding globulin or transcortin) increases, as a result of which the level of free biologically active cortisol remains normal. Excessive cortisol in adipocytes has a local lipolytic effect, stimulates adipogenesis in visceral depots, and also contributes to a decrease in the sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin and the development of insulin resistance. Due to changes in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system during pregnancy, the level of aldosterone increases, which leads to an increase in the volume of circulating blood and maintenance of a normal balance of sodium and potassium.

Serum aldosterone increases starting from the eighth week of pregnancy and increases up to tenfold by the time of delivery [6]. During pregnancy, the placenta produces pituitary-like hormones (human chorionic gonadotropin and corticotropin, placental lactogen, adrenocorticotrophic hormone), hypothalamic-like hormones (gonadotropic, corticotropic and thyroid-stimulating hormones, somatostatin), adipocyte-specific hormones such as leptin and resistin [11]. The placenta secretes a large number of cytokines (interleukin-1, interleukin-6, tumor necrosis factor), growth factors (insulin-like growth factor-1, epidermal growth factor, platelet and fibroblast growth factors, inhibin and activin) and pregnancy-specific proteins necessary for the growth and development of the fetus, immune relationships between mother and fetus, ensuring the maintenance of pregnancy [6, 10]. It has now been proven that in pregnant women, leptin is synthesized not only by adipocytes, but also by placental trophoblasts in quantities no less than in adipose tissue.

Placental leptin does not differ in structure and biological properties from adipose tissue leptin and is a product of the expression of the same gene (ob gene). The content of leptin in the blood serum directly correlates with body weight, the level of human chorionic gonadotropin and the gestational age.

The leptin level increases from the 6th-8th week, reaching a maximum in the II-III trimester of pregnancy, and significantly decreases after delivery. An inverse correlation has also been revealed between the leptin content in the blood serum of a pregnant woman and the condition of the children at birth. In the blood taken from the umbilical cord of newborns, the leptin level produced by the placenta, as well as the adipose tissue of the fetus, is directly proportional to the body weight and the mass of adipose tissue of the newborn; it is reduced in cases of maternal smoking, prematurity of the fetus, low anthropometric indicators in children born at term, and increased in very large newborns. It is assumed that the main role of placental leptin is participation in the regulation of fetal growth and

development, stimulation of hematopoiesis and lymphopoiesis in the newborn. Leptin contained in the mother's breast milk can also enter the gastrointestinal tract, and then into the blood of the newborn, thereby playing an additional role in the regulation of fetal growth.

There is evidence of the role of ghrelin during pregnancy. Ghrelin is a polypeptide hormone secreted primarily by cells of the gastric mucosa, causing a feeling of hunger and being a powerful stimulator of growth hormone secretion. It is known that ghrelin receptors are also located in the placenta [13]. The level of ghrelin increases with increasing gestational age, reaching a maximum by the middle of the second trimester of pregnancy [13]. The main role of ghrelin during pregnancy is to regulate the mother's appetite and increase energy consumption with food to ensure nutrition of the fetus. Ghrelin is also involved in the regulation of contractile activity of the myometrium.

Maternal Adaptations and Hormonal Interplay

1. Cardiovascular Adaptations. Estrogens and relaxin promote increased cardiac output and vascular compliance to meet the metabolic demands of pregnancy.
2. Metabolic Changes. hPL and cortisol contribute to maternal insulin resistance, ensuring adequate glucose supply to the fetus.
3. Immune Modulation. Progesterone and hCG suppress maternal immune responses to allow tolerance of the semi-allogeneic fetus.

Hormonal Imbalances and Pregnancy Complications

1. Preeclampsia. Linked to inadequate placentation and altered levels of angiogenic factors, including placental growth hormone.
2. Preterm Labor. Premature withdrawal of progesterone and increased prostaglandin production are major contributors.
3. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM). Excessive maternal insulin resistance due to hormonal dysregulation leads to hyperglycemia, affecting fetal growth.

Future Perspectives

Emerging therapies targeting hormonal pathways, such as progesterone supplementation for preterm birth prevention and anti-angiogenic treatments for preeclampsia, offer promising avenues. Advances in understanding placental hormone production and signaling will further enhance maternal and fetal care.

Conclusion

Hormones are indispensable in the regulation of pregnancy and fetal development, ensuring successful outcomes for both mother and baby. Disruptions in hormonal balance can lead to significant complications, highlighting the need for early diagnosis and targeted interventions. Continued research into the intricate hormonal networks during pregnancy will pave the way for improved therapeutic strategies and maternal-fetal health outcomes.

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